

**BACTERIA CONTAMINATION ON CAKES FROM SOME MAJOR BAKERS IN
YENAGOA METROPOLIS**

BY

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TO

DEPARTMENT OF MEDICAL LABORATORY SCIENCE

(MEDICAL MICROBIOLOGY OPTION)

FACULTY OF BASIC MEDICAL SCIENCES

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BACHELOR'S IN MEDICAL LABORATORY SCIENCE**

(B.MLS)

DEGREE IN MEDICAL LABORATORY SCIENCE

(MEDICAL MICROBIOLOGY OPTION)

SUPERVISED BY

MR. ARIKEPKAR IBEMOLOGI

JULY, 2023

DECLARATION

I, ADEWALE DEBORAH YETUNDE with matriculation number UG/015/0911 hereby declare that this research project on “BACTERIA CONTAMINATION ON CAKES FROM SOME MAJOR BAKERS IN YENAGOA METROPOLIS”; is my original work and has not been previously submitted to any other department or university for the award of degree.

ADEWALE DEBORAH YETUNDE

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Signature

Date

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this research project work titled "BACTERIA CONTAMINATION ON CAKES FROM SOME MAJOR BAKERS IN YENAGOA METROPOLIS" was carried out by **ADEWALE DEBORAH YETUNDE** with matriculation number **UG/015/0911** and hereby accepted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of Bachelor of Medical Laboratory Science B. MLS (Medical Microbiology Option) in Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State.

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(Project Supervisor)

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DEDICATION

This seminar work is dedicated to God Almighty who made this work a success.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I want to thank the Almighty God for His strength, grace, faithfulness, and mercy throughout this work.

I am greatly and forever indebted to my lovely parent and siblings for their immeasurable support, love and care. Thank you for believing in me and standing by me all the way.

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I also wish to extend my sincere gratitude to my wonderful friends for their encouragement. Thank you.

CHAPTER ONE

1.1 Background of the study

Cake is a cherished food source for people throughout the whole world and a good example of bakery products made from cereals (Saranraj, *et al.*, 2011). The word cake is derived from the Norse word "kaka" which is from the Viking origin. According to food historians, the first culture to show evidence of baking skills and interest were the ancient Egyptians. It is said that cakes have their part to play in ancient beliefs and superstitions of which some still carry on to modern times. Cakes were modifications of bread baked with flour, sugar, fat, eggs and preservatives, with common additional ingredients such as fresh fruit, fruit preserves, nuts, cocoa, and extracts (vanilla). It can be filled with dessert sauces like custard, jelly, whipped cream or syrups, iced with butter cream or other icings, and decorated with marzipan, piped borders, or candied fruit. Cakes are used for special occasions such as wedding, birthdays, parties and special events. Despite these aesthetic properties of cakes, they are still subjected to spoilage problems which could be physical, chemical and microbiological spoilage. The nutritious nature of cake makes it highly susceptible to heavy microbial contamination and possible involvement in food poisoning. This is mainly attributed to the fact that its sources of contamination can be from the processing equipment, dirty containers as well as wrapping material. Cake is mainly packaged by hands which can enhance contact with food poisoning organisms such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, which is quite often found in human hands (Samphina Academy, 2023).

1.2 Statement of Research problem

Microbial contamination of cakes is an aspect of concern worldwide as its consumption in several occasions has led to food poisoning associated with diarrhea and several other symptoms after attending these events. It is therefore, important to determine the nature of bacteria that can contaminate cakes and devise mitigation techniques before outbreaks, as contamination of these cakes poses great danger to individuals.

1.3 Significance of the study

This study may help to reveal the prevalence of pathogenic bacteria on cakes used in special events and occasions in Yenagoa metropolis, Bayelsa state, and how it can be a major cause of

food poisoning, diarrhoea, dysentery and even cholera outbreak. The processing of this sample in the medical microbiology laboratory can evidently reveal the microbe that's likely to cause illness after consumption and proffer treatment options.

1.4 Aim of study

To isolate and identify bacteria that can be found on cakes in Yenagoa metropolis, Bayelsa state.

1.5 Objectives of study

1. To evaluate the spectrum of bacterial loads from each cake sampled.
2. To characterize the microbial isolates from the cakes collected from major bakers in Yenagoa metropolis, Bayelsa state.
3. To compare the isolates obtained from the different cake vendors in Yenagoa metropolis.

1.6 Research question

1. Can cakes eaten in parties and special events in Yenagoa metropolis carry pathogenic bacteria.
2. Which type(s) of bacteria is present on cakes in Yenagoa metropolis, Bayelsa state.
3. Which type(s) of bacteria is more prevalent on cakes in Yenagoa metropolis, Bayelsa state.

1.7 Research hypothesis

There are no pathogenic bacteria present on cakes consumed in Yenagoa metropolis.

1.8 Scope of Study

This study is confined to the isolation and identification of pathogenic bacteria on cakes collected from some major bakers in Yenagoa metropolis, Bayelsa state.

1.9 Limitations of study

1. The availability of financial resources during the project.
2. The time frame allotted for the research

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 CAKES

Cakes can be defined or referred to as form of food that is usually sweet and often baked. It is a cherished food source for people throughout the whole world. It is among the important types of food list and confectionery that varies in forms, colors, decorations and ingredients. Its rate of consumption during happy occasions is high and has also become part of the daily requirements to local consumer, where they are usually served with cold and hot drinks. As a baked product it has gained popularity because of its availability, ready to eat convenience and reasonably good shelf life and taste (Chappalwar, et al., 2013). Cakes are considered as high nutritional value food as it supplies the body building proteins, fats, carbohydrates, minerals and vitamins. The production of cakes can be time consuming and characterized by precise steps which includes the preparation of raw materials and cake mixture, baking, cooling, filling, coating and ornamenting. The main ingredient in cakes includes sugar, flour, eggs, milk, fats along with other materials such as colors, flavors, emulsifiers, as well as the materials of ornamentation, which include fruits, nuts, natural and artificial ornamental materials, i.e., flowers, toys and others, some form of leavening agent such as yeast or baking powder (Salunke and Bhosale, 2015).

2.2 HISTORY OF CAKES

It's so exciting that as common as cakes are, there are fascinating stories about its origin of which it starts with the word 'cake' itself, which is of the viking origin, from the Norse word "kaka". According to food historians, the first culture to show evidence of baking skills and interest were the ancient Egyptians as it was noted that they were fed up with meats and wanted to try something new. Cakes have their part to play in ancient beliefs and superstitions, some which still carries on to modern times. In olden times, people used cakes as offerings to their gods and spirits around the world. The Chinese celebrate Harvest Moon festival and have moon cakes to honor their moon goddess. This tradition continues up to today. Russians have sun cakes called blini which are thin pancakes to pay their respect to a deity called Maslenitsa. Ancient Celts rolled cakes down a hill during the Beltane festival held on the first day of spring to imitate solar movement. With such a rich history and connection of humans with cake, it is no wonder that they remain such an important part of our lives (Whats Cooking America, 2020).

2.3 TYPES OF CAKES

Cakes can be divided into several categories based on the following:

The ingredients and mixing techniques

The occasion for which they are intended for.

Types of Cakes Based on Ingredients and Mixing Techniques

1. **Butter cakes:** Butter cakes are made from creamed butter, sugar, eggs, flour and sometimes baking powder. They rely on the combination of butter and sugar beaten for an extended time to incorporate air into the batter. Another type of butter cake is the one that takes its names from the proportion of ingredients used as 1-2-3-4 cake: 1 cup butter, 2 cups sugar, 3 cups flour, and 4 eggs (Tartan, 2000).
2. **Sponge cakes:** Sponge cakes or foam cakes are cakes made from whipped eggs, sugar, and flour. Traditional sponge cakes are leavened only with eggs. They rely primarily on trapped air in a protein matrix of beaten eggs to provide leavening, sometimes with a bit of baking powder or other chemical leaven added. Egg-leavened sponge cakes are thought to be the oldest cakes made without yeast. Another type of sponge cake is the Angel food cake that is made of whites of the eggs and traditionally baked in a tube pan. And the French Genoise sponge cake that includes clarified butter. Highly decorated sponge cakes with lavish toppings are sometimes called *gateau*, the French word for cake. Chiffon cakes are also sponge cakes with vegetable oil, which adds moistness (Ureta, et.al., 2016).
3. **Chocolate cakes:** Chocolate cakes are butter cakes, sponge cakes, or other cakes flavored with melted chocolate or cocoa powder. German and Fudge cakes are variety of chocolate cakes (Balakrishnan, 2021).
4. **Coffee cake:** Coffee cake is generally thought of as a cake to serve with coffee or tea at breakfast or a coffee break. Some types use yeast as a leavening agent while others use baking soda or baking powder. These cakes often have a crumb topping called streusel or a light glaze drizzle.
5. **Flourless cake:** Baked flourless cakes include baked cheesecakes and flourless chocolate cakes.

6. Layer cakes: Layer cakes are cakes made with layers of sponge or butter cake, filled with cream, jam or other filling to hold the layers together.
7. One egg cake: One egg cake are made with one egg and can be made with butter or vegetable shortening. It's an economical recipe when using two eggs for each cake was too costly (Swangnop and Duangdee, 2019).

Types of Cakes Based on the Occasion for Which They Are Intended

Cakes may be classified according to the occasion for which they are intended while some types of cake may be associated with festivals. This special type of cakes includes:

1. Wedding cakes: The cutting of a wedding cake constitutes a social ceremony in some cultures. The Ancient Roman marriage ritual of *confarreatio* originated in the sharing of a cake.
2. Birthday cakes: A birthday cake is a cake eaten as part of a birthday celebration. While there is no standard for birthday cakes, they are typically decorated layer cakes covered in frosting, often featuring birthday wishes ("Happy birthday") and the celebrant's name or even picture. It's customary to serve birthday cakes with small lit candles on top, especially in the case of a child's birthday. Variations include cupcakes, cake pops, pastries, and tarts (Rusinek, 2011).
3. Cakes for first communion: This is a type of cake that symbolizes the innocence and purity of the young communicants. The cakes are usually simple and good, not showy or ostentatious.
4. Christmas/ Easter cakes: There has been a long tradition of decorating an iced cake at Christmas time. But there are other cakes associated with Christmas which include stolen cake, chocolate log and mince pies. While at Easter we have the babka and simnel cake, or mooncake.
5. Halloween cakes: A Halloween cake is a cake prepared with Halloween-themed decorations and symbols. It may be prepared using traditional Halloween colors such as black and orange and may be decorated in many diverse manners with various themes. It may be a part of the Halloween decorations in households that celebrate the holiday (Clark and Dodd, 2004).

6. Passover plava: this a type of sponge cake sometimes made with matzo meal.
7. A Lancashire Courting Cake: this is a type of fruit-filled cake baked by a fiancée for her betrothed. The cake has been described as "somewhere between a firm sponge with a greater proportion of flour to fat and eggs than a Victoria sponge cake and a shortbread base. It was a proof of the bride-to-be's baking skills". Traditionally it is a two-layer cake filled and topped with strawberries or raspberries and whipped cream (Food, 2023).

2.4 MICROBIAL SPOILAGE OF CAKES

Microbial spoilage of cake is the process in which the quality of cakes deteriorates to the extent that it renders the cake unacceptable for human consumption. Microbial spoilage is the major problem that causes deterioration in bakery products, and it's mainly caused by moulds, yeasts and occasionally by bacteria (Guynot, et.al., 2005). The interference between low pH, high and low water activity (aW), and filling materials may support the growth and production of toxins by microorganisms even when the individual ingredients do not support growth. Cakes and bakery products filled with custard, cream, and sauces can be spoiled by microorganisms because of the ingredients that are added after baking, such as icing, nuts, toppings, and cream. Most products, because of low water activity allow only molds to grow. However, many fillings support the growth of spoilage bacteria, especially if they have high water activity, near to neutral pH, and contain high protein ingredients such as meat, egg or milk. Ambient temperatures, pH levels between 5.4-7.5, and water activity in range of 0.75–0.98 promotes spoilage of baked products with mold, yeast, and spore forming bacteria. And cakes have water activity (aw) levels above 0.94 which is an important factor that influences spoilage of the products (Sperber, and Doyle, 2009).

2.5 PATHOGENIC BACTERIA THAT CAN BE FOUND ON CAKES

The pathogenic bacteria that have been isolated and identified on cake samples were *Bacillus* spp, *Staphylococcus* spp, *Micrococcus* spp, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas* spp, *Salmonella* spp, *Aeromonas* spp, *Shigella* spp., *Vibrio* spp., *Micrococcus* spp, *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* (Nazir and Islam, 2007). They are the common genera of bacteria and molds generally isolated from bakery products which are known to produce toxins, which are both acutely and chronically toxic to humans (Pundir and Jain 2011).

2.6 SOME SELECTED JOURNAL REVIEWED

Microorganisms associated with plain cake spoilage were evaluated by Ibejekwe, A.N., and Nyam, M.A (2018) from Eateries and Parties in Jos Metropolis, Nigeria.” Fifteen samples of the cakes were collected and cultured. Bacteria and Fungi were isolated using Nutrient and Czapek agar respectively. Three bacterial species and five fungal species were isolated from the spoilt cake samples. The bacterial isolated were, *Bacillus laterosporus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Fungal isolated were, *Rhizopus stolonifer*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Penicillium citrinum* and, *Penicillium chrysogenum*. The organisms isolated were listed in order of frequency of occurrence. It then means that most cakes sold in shops and served in parties were not properly prepared and preserved thus, there is a need to employ standard conditions in baking.

Sherif, et.al., (2018) examined pathogenic bacteria in some cake samples. He examined thirty cake samples of twelve different companies which were collected from Damietta and Dakahlia governorates in September and October 2012. All the samples were in production date except one (A4) was expired. The high contamination of examined cakes with mesophilic bacteria were found in the A4 sample (286.76×10^3 cfu/g) while the lowest value was found with the B22 sample (0.12×10^3 cfu/g). Samples of C11 (21.30×10^3) and A5 (0.07×10^3) cfu/g were the highest and the lowest values of thermophilic bacteria, respectively. Staphylococci presented in all examined cake samples except seven samples. The highest value was 3.50×10^3 cfu/g in C13 sample followed by 2.90×10^3 cfu/g in A14 sample. Aeromonas specie was presented in all examined cake except A4 sample. The highly contaminated samples with Aeromonas specie in case of A5 being 2.73×10^3 cfu/g. The pathogenic enteric bacilli were found in all examined cake samples except sixteen which gave negative results. Results in positive samples were between 0.02×10^3 to 0.23×10^3 cfu/g. In D28 and C13 respectively. Eleven samples gave negative results and nineteen were positive for coliform bacteria. Seven of the cake sample gave negative results of *Bacillus cereus* while other samples, while positive results ranged between 0.02×10^3 and 1.54×10^3 cfu/g in C21 and D9, respectively. Twenty examined samples do not have *Vibrio* spp. Results proved that C12 was the highest count being 2.92×10^3 cfu/g. All samples were not in conformity with the Egyptian Organization for Standardization and Quality of cake (ES: 4037/2005). Forty-two bacterial isolates were obtained and identified according to the microscopic and biochemical examination. Obtained bacterial isolates were identified as

Bacillus cereus, Bacillus subtilis, Aeromonas spp., Pseudomonas spp., Echerichia spp., Salmonella spp., Shigella spp., Vibrio spp., Micrococcus spp. and Staphylococcus aureus.

Study on “Microbiological Examination for some Chocolate Cakes” was carried out by Elfadaly, et.al., (2016) to determine the microbiological quality of chocolate cake samples. Samples were collected from different sites of local markets of Damietta and Dakahlia Governorates in September and October 2012. Microbiological examination of cake samples included: Total viable mesophilic count (TM), 30 °C/72h., Total thermophilic bacterial count (TT), 45 °C/72 h., Staphylococci count (SC), 37 °C/72 h., Aeromonas spp count (AS), 30 °C/48 h., Enteric bacilli count (EB), 30 °C/48 h., Coliform bacterial detection (CD), 30 °C/24 h., Bacillus cereus count (BC), 37 °C/72 h., Vibrio spp count (VS), 37 °C/72 h. and Fungi count (TF), 25 °C/6 days. The obtained results showed that, the highest value of TM was A4 being $>2 \times 10^5$ colony forming unit/ gram (cfu/g). But the lowest value was B22 being $>1 \times 10^2$ cfu/g. All samples gave a positive result of TT; the highest value of TT was A8 being $> 1 \times 10^4$ cfu/g. The results of SC were not found in 6 samples, while 9 sample gave a positive result varied between 3.7×10^1 to $>1 \times 10^3$ cfu/g. AS was presented in all samples except A4 samples. EB was present in nine samples. BC count was not in all samples, but maximum value was $>1 \times 10^3$ cfu/g. VS was presented in seven samples. TF was also counted, and the highest values was in A4 being $>1 \times 10^3$ cfu/g and the lowest value was in B27 being 27 cfu/g. Finally, all samples were not in conformity with the standard specifications of the Egyptian cake (ES: 4037/2005). Five isolates of fungi were isolated from cake samples, The microscopic examination with light microscope and scanning electron microscope (SEM) showed that isolates were identified as Rhizopus stolonifer and Aspergillus niger.

Another study by Letacia, et.al., (2018) looks at “Fungi in Cake Production Chain: Occurrence and Evaluation of Growth Potential in Different Cake Formulations During Storage”. This study determines the prevalence and populations of fungi in cake production chain. Besides, the growth potential of twelve fungal strains in different cake formulations was evaluated. Raw materials from two different batches ($n = 143$), chocolate cakes ($n = 30$), orange cakes ($n = 20$), and processing environment air samples ($n = 147$) were analyzed. Among the raw materials, wheat flour (3.2 ± 0.3 log CFU per g) and corn meal (3.8 ± 0.8 log CFU per g) belonging to

batch #1 showed significant higher fungal counts ($p < 0.05$). The fungal counts in the processing environment air reached up to 2.56 log CFU per m^3 ($p < 0.05$). The predominant fungi species in the industrialized cakes were *Aspergillus flavus* (28.15%), *Penicillium citrinum* (18.45%), *Penicillium paxilli* (14.56%), and *Aspergillus niger* (6.8%), which were also detected in the raw materials and processing environment air. Only *Penicillium glabrum* and *Penicillium citrinum* showed visible mycelium (> 3 mm) in the free of preservative cake formulation at 19th and 44th days of storage at 25 °C, respectively. Revealing the biodiversity of fungi in ingredients, air and final products, as well as challenging final products with representative fungal strains may assist to implement effective controlling measures as well as to gather data for the development of more robust cake formulations.

According to the survey from “Food safety Authority of Ireland, (2018)” Investigations on Microbiological Safety of Ready-to-eat (RTE) Cakes, pastries and desserts with high-risk fillings were made. Samples (n=997) were collected from April to June 2014 and were tested for four microbiological parameters. The overall microbiological quality of the samples tested was satisfactory. Of the 997 samples tested, 100% were satisfactory for Salmonella and Listeria monocytogenes. A low level (10 cfu/g) of L. monocytogenes serovar 1/2a was cultured from one sample of an “all custard slice” but was enumerated below the food safety criteria limit of 100 cfu/g. 1 Of 997 samples tested for presumptive Bacillus cereus, 99.3% (n=990) were satisfactory and 0.3% (n=3/997) were acceptable. Unsatisfactory levels of presumptive B. cereus were enumerated in 0.3% (n=3/997) of samples and 0.1% (n=1/997) had levels considered to be unacceptable/potentially hazardous. Satisfactory levels of coagulase-positive staphylococci were enumerated in 98.1% (n=970/989) of samples and acceptable levels were enumerated in 1.5% (n=15/989) of samples. Unsatisfactory levels of coagulase positive staphylococci were enumerated in 0.3% (n=3/989) of samples and 0.1% (n=1/989) had levels considered to be unacceptable/potentially hazardous. The cakes, pastries and desserts identified with high levels of microbial contamination contained fresh dairy cream, custard or soft cheese. No issues were identified with samples containing raw or lightly cooked egg. The storage/display temperature for three unsatisfactory and two unacceptable/potentially hazardous samples were observed to be >5 °C, indicating the likely importance of temperature control in these types of foods to limit the growth of bacteria and thereby reduce the risk of gastrointestinal illness.

Antai Godwin. (2013) from the Department of Science and Technology carried out a study about the Microbial Analysis of Icing Sugar of Spoiled Cake and its Implications in Ikot Ekpene metropolis in Akwa Ibom state. Samples of cake were collected from bakeries and eateries in Ikot Ekpene, Akwa Ibom. Microorganisms associated with cake spoilage were evaluated. This research assesses the following topics: economic importance of bakery products, microbial spoilage of bakery products, physical factors affecting microbial growth, control of microbial growth in bakery products by using chemical preservatives and bio preservatives. Bacteria and Fungi were isolated using Nutrient and Czapek agar respectively. Three bacterial species and five fungal species were isolated from the spoilt cake samples. The bacterial isolated were, *Bacillus laterosporus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Fungal isolated were, *Rhizopus stolonifer*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Penicillium citrinum* and, *Penicillium chrysogenum*. The organisms isolated were listed in order of frequency of occurrence. It then means that most cakes sold in shops and served in parties were not properly prepared and preserved thus, there is a need to employ standard conditions in baking.

Microbial Analysis of Ragi Cake Base Stored at Room Temperature without Added Chemical Preservative was made by Chaudhari, et.al., (2017) where Microbial analysis was said to be an essential part of food safety. In the study ragi cake base was analysed for microbial tests. All the samples were taken in triplicates. Specific media were used for identification of different microbes (yeast, mould, bacteria). For the identification and microbial analysis Total Plate Count (TPC), Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) were used and for confirmation of number of colonies. In this study, the cake base samples were prepared without added chemical preservative and stored at room temperature were used for microbial analysis. Ragi cake was prepared with ragi flour and refined wheat flour in proportion of 50:50 and condensed milk, butter, baking powder, baking soda, aerated water and cocoa powder. The microbiological quality of ragi cake base was monitored by analyzing the total plate count (TPC) and yeast and mold count (Y&M). Results obtained in this study revealed that Ragi cake base stored at room temperature spoiled about 3.5 times faster than stored at chilled temperature. At room temperature storage, the cakes become moldy on the 8th day with the highest TPC of 6.05 log₁₀ CFU and Y&M count of 6.21 log₁₀ CFU.

CHAPTER THREE

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Study Design

This is a cross-sectional survey of microorganisms on cakes from some major bakers in Yenagoa metropolis, Bayelsa state.

3.2 Study Area

This study was carried out in Yenagoa metropolis, Bayelsa state from the department of Medical Laboratory Science, Faculty of Basic Medical Science, College of Health Sciences, Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State Nigeria.

3.3 Ethical Approval

Ethical approval was obtained from the ethical Committee of the University.

3.4 Study Duration

The study was conducted during the period April-June 2023.

3.5 Reagents/Media

The media and reagents used for this research includes Nutrient agar, MacConkey agar, Salmonella Shigella agar, Sabroaud agar, Simmons Citrate agar, Hydrogen peroxide, Kovacs Reagent, Tryptone broth, Plasma, Tetramethyl-p-phenylene diamine dihydrochloride (Oxidase Reagent), Urease broth, Kligler Iron agar, Crystal violet, Lugol Iodine, Alcohol, Safranin, Normal saline, Distilled water, Sterile water, Methylated spirit and filter paper.

3.6 Sample Collection

A bacteriological survey was conducted on 10 cakes baked from 10 different cake vendors in Yenagoa metropolis. The cakes were freshly baked and carefully handled just like a normal cake

made for special events and were promptly transported to the Medical Microbiology laboratory of the Department of Medical Laboratory Science, Niger Delta University Wilberforce Island.

3.7 Serial Dilution and Culturing

Serial dilution is the process that requires a stepwise series of dilutions of an organism (bacteria) in fixed volumes of liquid diluents usually in a multiple of 10 in order to estimate the concentration of the sample. Each of the cake Sample was put in a bijou bottle containing 5ml of sterile water. Then into 6 test tubes labeled 10^{-1} , 10^{-2} , 10^{-3} , 10^{-4} , 10^{-5} and 10^{-6} was added 9ml of sterile water each. With the aid of a sterile pipette, 1ml of the sample was collected from the bijou bottle into tube labeled 10^{-1} and mixed, 1ml from tube labeled 10^{-1} was collected into tube labeled 10^{-2} and mixed, 1ml was collected from tube labeled 10^{-2} into tube labeled 10^{-3} and mixed, 1ml was collected from tube labeled 10^{-3} into tube labeled 10^{-4} and mixed, 1ml was collected from tube labeled 10^{-4} into tube labeled 10^{-5} and mixed, 1ml was collected from tube labeled 10^{-5} and put into tube labeled 10^{-6} (APHA, 1998). Then 0.1ml from tube 6 was inoculated onto Nutrient agar, Macconkey agar and Salmonella *Shigella* agar and Sabraud agar using the spread plate techniques.

3.8 Sample Processing

The isolation of the cake sample was carried out using the method described by Ayanda., *et al.* (2013). The samples were soaked in sterile water for 30 minutes to dissolve. Each sample was subjected to serial dilution and inoculated in duplicate onto MacConkey agar, CLED agar, SSA agar and Sabrouad agar plates that were prepared according to manufacturer's instructions and then sterilized using the autoclave at a temperature of 121°C for 15 minutes. All the inoculated plates were incubated for 24 hours at 37°C . After the overnight incubation, the plates were removed from the incubator and presumptively observed for colony characteristics. Isolated colonies were then sub-cultured into slants for proper preliminary identification. Single isolated colonies from the slants and plates were subjected to Gram's staining and standard biochemical tests (Catalase, Coagulase, Indole, oxidase, KIA, and Citrate Utilization tests) (Chesebrough, 2000).

3.9 Spread Plate Technique

The spread plate technique is a process that is used to culture samples for total colony count. 0.1ml from the tube labeled 10^{-6} was inoculated on to the agar plates and spread using a sterile glass rod. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24hours. The total colonies were calculated in colony forming units per ml (CFU/ml).

3.10 Characterization and Identification of Bacterial Isolates

Bacterial isolates were characterized using colonial, microscopic and biochemical characteristics.

3.10.1 Colonial Morphology (Macroscopic Examination) of Bacterial Isolates

Bacterial isolates were first differentiated by macroscopic examination of their colonies. The colonies were differentiated based on size, color, pigmentation, elevation, surface texture, margin (Barrow and Feltham, 1993).

3.10.2 Gram Stain

Gram staining is an essential step that identifies Gram positive and Gram-negative isolates based on their cell wall composition. For gram positive, their cell wall was purple because they retain the primary stain, which is crystal violet, while gram negative bacteria were stained pink, because they retain counter stains. The procedure was carried out as follows; smear was made from overnight culture on a clean grease free glass slide. The smear was left to air dry and then fixed by passing through flame, its allowed to cool before staining. Then the slide was flooded with crystal violet stain for 60 seconds and rinsed in water. Lugol's iodine was added for 60 seconds and rinsed in water. It was then decolorized rapidly (few seconds) with acetone alcohol and rinsed immediately. Finally, the smear was covered with safranin stain for 2 minutes and rinsed in water. The back of slide was wiped clean and placed in a draining rack for smear to air dry. A drop of immersion oil was placed to the dried smear and examined under the light microscope using the X100 objective lens. (Cheesbrough, 2006).

3.11 Biochemical Tests

Biochemical test was performed for the identification and confirmatory tests of the organism. And the organisms used for inoculation of the test media were sourced from fresh cultures. Specific biochemical tests performed include Catalase test, Coagulase test, Kilger iron agar test,

Urease test, Indole production test, Citrate utilization test, and Oxidase test. (Cheesbrough, 2009).

3.11.1 Catalase Test

This test is used to detect the presence of the enzymes catalase which differentiate bacteria species based on their positive or negative reaction with hydrogen peroxide solution. Catalase test was carried out by putting 2ml of hydrogen peroxide into a sterile test tube, then few colonies of the test organism were picked with a sterile applicator stick and emulsified in the hydrogen peroxide and it was observed for effervescence or active bubbling (Cheesbrough, 2006).

3.11.2 Coagulase Test

This test detects the presence of enzyme coagulase. The slide method was used, where a drop of normal saline was placed on each end of a clean grease-free slide. A colony of the test isolates was collected with sterile wire loop and emulsified with the drop of normal saline on each end to make two thick suspensions. A loopful of fresh human plasma was dropped on one end of the suspension and mixed gently using a sterile wire loop. The suspension on the other end was left as control. It was observed for clumping. (Cheesbrough, 2006).

3.11.3 Sugar Fermentation, Gas and H₂S Production (KIA)

This test was carried out to identify the isolate to species level as the production of turbidity and gas from carbohydrates (lactose, glucose, sucrose, manitol) was used to identify isolates. A tube of Kligler Iron Agar was inoculated using a sterile straight wire loop, first the butt was stabbed then the slope was streaked and incubated at 35–37°C overnight. Lactose fermenting bacteria appeared as yellow butt and yellow slope, glucose fermenting bacteria appeared as yellow butt and red slope, non-lactose and non- glucose fermenting bacteria appeared as red butt and red slope, blackening in the media indicated hydrogen sulphide production and cracks in the medium was due to gas production (Cheesbrough, 2006).

3.11.4 Citrate Utilization Test

This test is used to identify enteric bacteria. *Enterobacter* Spp are positive to this test, while *Escherichia coli* will give a negative reaction. The test is used to check the ability of organisms to utilize citrate as a sole carbon source. Bacteria that can use citrate can also extract nitrogen from ammonium salt with production of ammonia. The isolate was inoculated aseptically using a sterile wire loop to streak on simmon's citrate Agar medium. It was then incubated for 24-48hours. After incubation at 38°C, a blue colouration on the medium indicates a positive reaction, while no change in the colour of the medium, indicates a negative reaction to citrate test. (Cheesbrough, 2006).

3.11.5 Indole Test

Indole production is an important characteristic in the identification of many species of microorganisms. Indole is one of metabolic degradation products of the amino acid tryptophan. The test is based on the formation of a red complex when indole reacts with aldehyde group of p-dimethyl-amino benzaldehyde which is the active chemical in kovac reagent. Tryptophan broth was inoculated with the test organism and incubated at 37°C for 18 to 24 hours. At the end of incubation period few drops of kovac reagent were added, and the development of red color at the interface of the reagent and broth within seconds after adding the reagent was an indicator of presence of indole (Cheesbrough, 2006).

3.11.6 Urease Test

The test was used to determine the ability of organisms to produce the enzyme urease, which hydrolyzes urea. Hydrolysis of urea produces ammonia; the formation of ammonia alkalizes the medium and the pH shift was detected by the color change of phenol red from light orange to magenta which indicated a positive result. A well-isolated colony was picked from the surface of the medium and inoculated as single streak on the slant surface of Christensen's urea agar (Cheesbrough, 2006).

3.11.7 Oxidase Test

This test detects the presence of cytochrome C oxidase that can reduce oxygen by oxidizing the oxidase reagent (tetramethyl-p-phenylenediaminedihydrochloride) to give a dark-blue color. The test was performed by commercial discs impregnated with the oxidase reagent; a pure colony

was smeared on the disc by sterile wooden stick. A positive reaction to oxidase test is indicated by a deep purple color within 10 seconds while the other colors or no change in color indicates a negative reaction. (Cheesbrough, 2006).

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

Table 4.1 Prevalance of Bacteria Isolated from Ten different Cake Samples in Yenagoa Metropolis

Bacteria	Source	Day 1- No of Isolates (%)	Day 3- No of Isolates (%)	Day 7- No of Isolates (%)
<i>Bacillus Spp</i>	Cake	4(5.6)	2(2.9)	0(0)
<i>Pseudomonas Spp</i>	Cake	6(8.3)	4(5.8)	0(0)
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	Cake	28(38.9)	18(26.5)	18(24.3)
<i>Candida Spp</i>	Cake	0(0)	12(17.6)	12(16.2)
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	Cake	6(8.3)	6(8.8)	2(2.7)
<i>Proteus Spp</i>	Cake	4(5.6)	6(8.8)	0(0)
<i>Salmonella Spp</i>	Cake	0(0)	6(8.8)	20(27.0)
<i>Candida albican</i>	Cake	14(19.4)	4(5.8)	4(5.4)
<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	Cake	2(2.8)	4(5.8)	8(10.8)
<i>Streptococcus Spp</i>	Cake	6(8.3)	4(5.8)	0(0)
<i>Klebsiella Spp</i>	Cake	0(0)	2(2.9)	0(0)
<i>Micrococcus Spp</i>	Cake	0(0)	0(0)	6(8.1)
<i>Aeromonas Spp</i>	Cake	2(2.8)	0(0)	4(5.4)
Total		72(100)	68(100)	74(100)

TABLE 4.1 shows the percentage and number of occurrences of suspected bacteria identified from the cake samples collected from major bakers in Yenagoa metropolis. 72 organisms were isolated from the day1 samples where the highest occurring bacteria was *Escherichia coli* with 28(38.9%), followed by *Candida albican* 14(19.4%), *Pseudomonas Spp*, *Staphylococcus aureus*

and *Streptococcus Spp* had the same occurrence of 6(8.3%). The occurrence of *Bacillus Spp* was 4(5-6%), *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Aeromonas Spp* has 2(2.8%) occurrences. On the day 3, 68 organisms were isolated from same samples and *Escherichia coli* has the highest occurrence of 18(26.5%), followed by *Candida Spp* 12(17.6%). *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus Spp* and *Salmonella Spp* have the same occurrence of 6(8.8%). *Pseudomonas Spp*, *Candida albican*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Streptococcus Spp* has same occurrence of 4(5.8%). *Bacillus Spp* and *Klebsiella Spp* have same occurrence of 2(2.9%). On day 7 for same samples, 74 organisms were isolated, and the highest occurring organism was *Salmonella Spp* with 20(27.0%) followed by *Escherichia coli* with 18(24.3%). Next to *Escherichia coli* in occurrence was *Candida Spp* with 12(16.2%) followed by *Staphylococcus epidermidis* 8(10.8%). *Micrococcus Spp* occurrence was 6(8.1%), *Aeromonas Spp* and *Candida albican* were 4(5.1%) respectively and *Staphylococcus aureus* 2(2.7%).

Figure 4.1 Frequency of Bacteria isolated on Day 1 from Cake in $\text{Log}_{10}(\text{CFU/ML})$

Figure 4.1 Shows the graphical representation of data collected from the $\text{log}_{10}(\text{CFU/ML})$. Where $\text{log}_{10}(\text{CFU/ML})$ values from 9.4 above shows the highest frequency, 8.6, 8.8, 9.0 and 9.2 were below 10 and 9.6 have no frequency at all. The mean value of $\text{log}_{10}(\text{CFU/ML})$ was 9.29322172209 and standard deviation of 16812947435 in 74 isolates from 10 sampled cakes on day 1.

Figure 4.2 Frequency of Bacteria isolated on Day 3 from Cake in $\text{Log}_{10}(\text{CFU/ML})$

Figure 4.2 Shows the graphical representation of data collected from the $\text{log}_{10}(\text{CFU/ML})$. Where $\text{log}_{10}(\text{CFU/ML})$ values from 9.3 above shows the highest frequency, followed by 9.0. Ranges between 8.4 and 8.7 respectively have no frequency and 8.1 was below 10. The mean value of $\text{log}_{10}(\text{CFU/ML})$ was 9.2624458338 and standard deviation of 1942393721 in 68 isolates from 10 sampled cakes on day 3.

Figure 4.3 Frequency of Bacteria isolated on Day 7 from Cake in $\text{Log}_{10}(\text{CFU/ML})$

Figure 4.3 Shows the graphical representation of data collected from the $\text{log}_{10}(\text{CFU/ML})$. Where $\text{log}_{10}(\text{CFU/ML})$ values from 9.4 above shows the highest frequency, followed by ranges between 9.2 and 9.3 respectively. Ranges between 9.0, 9.1 and 9.5 have frequency below 10. The mean value of $\text{log}_{10}(\text{CFU/ML})$ was 9.2705255325 and standard deviation of 1212079115 in 74 isolates from 10 sampled cakes on day 7.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Discussion

Cakes as an attractive form of baked food would have been thought to be a perfect form of food that can pose no harm to human health. But the results obtained from this research study has revealed a high level of bacterial contamination on cakes, of which some are highly pathogenic, and some can be considered as pathogenic only in immunosuppressed patients as considerable number of both gram positive and gram-negative bacteria were isolated. The bacteria isolated were *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella Spp*, *Pseudomonas Spp*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Streptococcus Spp*, *Proteus Spp*, *Bacillus Spp*, *Aeromonas Spp*, *Micrococcus Spp*, *Klebsiella Spp*, and the fungi isolated were *Candida albican* and *Candida Spp*. These organisms isolated are in correspondence with those stated in reviewed literatures as possible organisms that is associated with cake spoilage and contamination (Sherif, et.al., 2018), (Ibejekwe, A.N., and Nyam, M.A 2018). While the fungi isolated is quite different from those stated in reviewed literature. Fungal growth is not of much importance to this study but *Candida Spp* as one of the common fungi species were isolated severally and this can be because baking yeast may be present in some of the ingredients used in baking and may also be from talking while baking as its can be found in the human gut (Letacia, et.al., 2018). *Escherichia coli* was seen as the bacteria with the highest reoccurrence, and this can be because most strains of *E. coli* are part of the normal flora of the gut, therefore, during baking the possibility of the baker to contaminate the cake while talking is high. The second most prevalent bacteria were *Salmonella Spp*, and since *Salmonella* can be transferred from animal to human and from human to human, it means that during baking, packaging, or storage the cake can be infected with feces by either fly

or human and other intracellular pathogens. *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Staphylococcus aureus* were Gram-positive bacteria isolated which are part of the normal human flora on the skin especially, it is usually not pathogenic but patients with compromised immune systems are at risk of developing infection. Being part of the normal skin flora, it can be a frequent cause of contaminant on cakes during its process. *Pseudomonas Spp* was also isolated in the cake samples, and this can be attributed to *Pseudomonas* milk spoilage or related ingredients from the cake (Wiedmann et al., 2000 and Marchand et al., 2009). Two major diseases are associated with *Aeromonas spp* isolate and they're gastroenteritis and wound infections, with or without bacteremia. Gastroenteritis typically occurs after the ingestion of contaminated water or food, whereas wound infections result from exposure to contaminated water. In its most severe form, *Aeromonas spp* can cause necrotizing fasciitis, which is life-threatening, therefore, cakes can get contaminated through the source of water used in baking (Minnaganti, et al., 2000). *Proteus spp.* bacteria are mostly known as opportunistic human pathogens that can be isolated from different human and non-human environments and they're present in higher organisms, soil, and water which could be the source of contaminants on the cake (Drzewiecka, and Sidorczyk, 2005). *Bacillus spp* exhibit a wide range of physiologic abilities that allow them to live in every natural environment which of course the baking process of this cakes must have been exposed to the environment either through purchase of the ingredients or where they're baked (Turnbull, 1996). Many *Streptococci spp* are not pathogenic, and form part of the commensal human microbiota of the mouth, skin, intestine, and upper respiratory tract which are source through which the cake can be contaminated. *Micrococcus spp* occurs in a wide range of environments too, including water, dust, and soil while *Klebsiella spp* infections are typically "nosocomial" infections, which means they're contracted in a hospital or healthcare setting

(Bagley, 2019). It is also not airborne and can't be contracted by breathing the same air as an infected person. So, finding it in cake sample could be that the baker or someone around the baker has been exposed to a hospital setting prior to baking.

5.2 Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that this research work has public health implications as the possible microorganisms (bacteria and fungi) that invades or contaminates cakes were evaluated. This signifies that the cakes served in parties and major events are contaminated even before it reaches the consumer and that some of the organisms may be increasingly expressed as its days of storage increases. Therefore, there is an urgent need to educate bakers on the need to adopt standard baking methods and conditions to reduce and eradicate food poisoning by these microorganisms.

5.3 Recommendation

Based on the above findings, the following is recommended

- General and personal hygiene should be maintained by bakers.
- Bakers should pay more attention to their environment by fumigating regularly to avoid flies while they're working.
- Proper washing and cleaning of hands before and after baking and when necessary.
- Towels used during baking should be regularly and properly washed.
- Communication during baking should be avoided as much as possible.
- Health workers who are bakers should take their PPE and personal hygiene seriously to avoid contaminating the cakes with hospital acquired infections.

- Health workers who are bakers should make sure they don't use the wears they have on in the hospital to the marketplace and their baking environment.

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APPENDIX

SAMPLE	TOTAL COLONY COUNT		
	COLONY COUNT	COLONY FORMING UNIT PER ML	LOG ₁₀ (CFU/ML)
	DAY 1		
S1 NA	245	2.5x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.389166084
S1 NA(2)	130	1.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.113943352
S1 MAC	200	2.0x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.301029996
S1 MAC(2)	202	2.0x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.305351369
S1 SSA	237	2.4x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.374748346
S1 SSA(2)	241	2.4x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.382017043
S1 SAB	200	2.0x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.301029996
S1 SAB(2)	225	2.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.352182518
S2 NA	294	2.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.46834733
S2 NA(2)	290	2.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.462397998
S2 MAC	300	3.0x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.477121255
S2 MAC(2)	285	2.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.45484486
S2 SSA	300	3.0x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.477121255
S2 SSA(2)	250	2.5x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.397940087
S2 SAB	289	2.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.460897843
S2 SAB(2)	223	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.348304863
S3 NA	203	2.0x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.307496038
S3 NA(2)	275	2.8x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.439332694
S3 MAC	226	2.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.354108439
S3 MAC(2)	248	2.5x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.394451681
S3 SSA	225	2.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.352182518
S3 SSA(2)	328	3.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.515873844
S3 SAB	155	1.6x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.11903317
S3 SAB(2)	178	1.8x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.250420002
S4 NA	217	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.336459734
S4 NA(2)	213	2.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.328379603
S4 MAC	123	1.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.089905111
S4 MAC(2)	259	2.6x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.413299764

S4 SSA	239	2.4x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.378397901
S4 SSA(2)	294	2.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.46834733
S5 NA	233	2.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.367355921
S5 NA(2)	225	2.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.352182518
S5 MAC	228	2.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.357934847
S5 MAC(2)	218	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.338456494
S5 SSA	224	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.350248018
S5 SSA(2)	261	2.6x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.416640507
S6 NA	200	2.0x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.301029996
S6 NA(2)	289	2.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.460897843
S6 MAC	123	1.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.089905111
S6 MAC(2)	131	1.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.117271296
S6 SSA	211	2.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.324282455
S6 SSA(2)	206	2.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.31386722
S7 NA	256	2.6x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.408239965
S7 NA(2)	227	2.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.356025857
S7 MAC	156	1.6x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.193124598
S7 MAC(2)	127	1.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.103803721
S7 SSA	226	2.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.354108439
S7 SSA(2)	219	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.340444115
S7 SAB	118	1.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.071882007
S7 SAB(2)	105	1.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.021189299
S8 NA	215	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.33243846
S8 NA(2)	218	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.338456494
S8 MAC	286	2.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.456366033
S8 MAC(2)	291	2.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.463892989
S8 SSA	234	2.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.369215857
S8 SSA(2)	229	2.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.359835482
S8 SAB	105	1.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.021189299
S8 SAB(2)	97	9.7x10 ⁸ CFU/ML	8.986771734
S9 NA	112	1.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.049218023
S9 NA(2)	109	1.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.037426498
S9 MAC	275	2.8x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.439332694
S9 MAC(2)	268	2.7x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.428134794
S9 SSA	148	1.5x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.170261715
S9 SSA(2)	146	1.5x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.164352856
S9 SAB	194	1.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.28780173
S9 SAB(2)	188	1.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.274157849
S10 NA	46	4.6x10 ⁸ CFU/ML	8.662757832

S10 NA(2)	58	5.8x10 ⁸ CFU/ML	8.763427994
S10 MAC	294	2.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.46834733
S10			
MAC(2)	279	2.8x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.445604203
S10 SSA	203	2.0x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.307496038
S10 SSA(2)	187	1.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.271841607
S10 SAB	115	1.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.06069784
S10 SAB(2)	122	1.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.086359831

DAY 3

S1 NA	294	2.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.46834733
S1 NA(2)	213	2.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.328379603
S1 MAC	268	2.7x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.428134794
S1 MAC(2)	227	2.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.356025857
S1 SSA	83	8.3x10 ⁸ CFU/ML	8.919078092
S1 SSA(2)	15	1.5x10 ⁸ CFU/ML	8.176091259
S1 SAB	86	8.6x10 ⁸ CFU/ML	8.934498451
S1 SAB(2)	92	9.2x10 ⁸ CFU/ML	8.963787827
S2 NA	292	2.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.465382851
S2 NA(2)	300	3.0x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.477121255
S2 MAC	185	1.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.267171728
S2 MAC(2)	218	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.338456494
S2 SSA	236	2.4x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.372912003
S2 SSA(2)	185	1.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.267171728
S2 SAB	153	1.5x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.184691431
S2 SAB(2)	118	1.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.071882007
S3 NA	193	1.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.285557309
S3 NA(2)	208	2.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.318063335
S3 MAC	286	2.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.456366033
S3 MAC(2)	218	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.338456494
S3 SSA	171	1.7x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.23299611
S3 SSA(2)	112	1.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.049218023
S3 SAB	222	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.346352975
S3 SAB(2)	232	2.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.365487985
S4 NA	286	2.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.456366033
S4 NA(2)	279	2.8x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.445604203
S4 MAC	216	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.334453751
S4 MAC(2)	248	2.5x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.394451681
S4 SSA	253	2.5x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.403120521

S4 SSA(2)	268	2.7x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.428134794
S4 SAB	222	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.346352975
S4 SAB(2)	219	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.340444115
S5 NA	281	2.8x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.44870632
S5 NA(2)	278	2.8x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.444044796
S5 MAC	268	2.7x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.428134794
S5 MAC(2)	274	2.7x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.437750563
S5 SSA	179	1.8x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.252853031
S5 SSA(2)	174	1.7x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.240549248
S5 SAB	112	1.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.049218023
S5 SAB(2)	115	1.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.06069784
S6 NA	122	1.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.086359831
S6 NA(2)	143	1.4x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.155336038
S6 SSA	120	1.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.079181246
S6 SSA(2)	124	1.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.093421685
S7 NA	129	1.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.11058971
S7 NA(2)	138	1.4x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.139879086
S7 MAC	145	1.5x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.161368003
S7 MAC(2)	153	1.5x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.184691431
S7 SSA	243	2.4x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.385606274
S7 SSA(2)	267	2.7x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.426511261
S7 SAB	223	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.348304863
S7 SAB(2)	205	2.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.311753861
S8 NA	232	2.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.365487985
S8 NA(2)	229	2.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.359835482
S8 MAC	215	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.33243846
S8 MAC(2)	244	2.4x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.387389826
S8 SSA	192	1.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.283301229
S8 SSA(2)	184	1.8x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.264817823
S8 SAB	215	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.33243846
S8 SAB(2)	129	1.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.11058971
S9 NA	193	1.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.285557309
S9 NA(2)	115	1.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.06069784
S9 MAC	194	1.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.28780173
S9 MAC(2)	207	2.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.315970346
S9 SSA	178	1.8x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.260071388
S9 SSA(2)	182	1.8x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.260071388
S10 NA	186	1.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.269512944
S10 NA(2)	184	1.8x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.264817823

DAY 7

S1 NA	246	2.5x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.390935107
S1 NA(2)	224	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.350248018
S1 MAC	282	2.8x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.450249108
S1 MAC(2)	287	2.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.457881897
S1 SSA	231	2.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.36361198
S1 SSA(2)	236	2.4x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.372912003
S1 SAB	122	1.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.086359831
S1 SAB(2)	112	1.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.049218023
S2 NA	111	1.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.045322979
S2 NA(2)	163	1.6x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.212187604
S2 MAC	128	1.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.10720997
S2 MAC(2)	221	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.344392274
S2 SSA	291	2.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.463892989
S2 SSA(2)	284	2.8x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.45331834
S2 SAB	218	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.338456494
S2 SAB(2)	209	2.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.320146286
S3 NA	148	1.5x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.170261715
S3 NA(2)	139	1.4x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.1430148
S3 MAC	264	2.6x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.421603927
S3 MAC(2)	276	2.8x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.440909082
S3 SSA	217	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.336459734
S3 SSA(2)	204	2.0x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.31386722
S3 SAB	166	1.7x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.220108088
S3 SAB(2)	162	1.6x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.209515015
S4 NA	215	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.33243846
S4 NA(2)	227	2.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.356025857
S4 MAC	119	1.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.075546961
S4 MAC(2)	276	2.8x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.440909082
S4 SSA	186	1.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.269512944
S4 SSA(2)	174	1.7x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.240549248
S4 SAB	192	1.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.283301229
S4 SAB(2)	188	1.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.274157849
S5 NA	222	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.346352975
S5 NA(2)	124	1.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.093421685
S5 SSA	112	1.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.049218023
S5 SSA(2)	294	2.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.46834733

S6 NA	157	1.6x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.195899652
S6 NA(2)	174	1.7x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.240549248
S6 MAC	214	2.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.330413773
S6 MAC(2)	203	2.0x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.307496038
S6 SSA	200	2.0x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.301029996
S6 SSA(2)	192	1.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.283301229
S6 SAB	186	1.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.269512944
S6 SAB(2)	208	2.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.318063335
S7 NA	225	2.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.352182518
S7 NA(2)	212	2.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.326335861
S7 MAC	192	1.9x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.283301229
S7 MAC(2)	208	2.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.318063335
S7 SSA	168	1.7x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.225309282
S7 SSA(2)	179	1.8x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.252853031
S7 SAB	264	2.6x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.421603927
S7 SAB(2)	272	2.7x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.434568904
S8 NA	248	2.5x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.394451681
S8 NA(2)	237	2.4x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.374748346
S8 MAC	128	1.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.10720997
S8 MAC(2)	134	1.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.127104798
S8 SSA	182	1.8x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.260071388
S8 SSA(2)	179	1.8x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.252853031
S9 NA	116	1.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.064457989
S9 NA(2)	128	1.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.10720997
S9 MAC	211	2.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.324282455
S9 MAC(2)	176	1.8x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.245512668
S9 SSA	169	1.7x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.227886705
S9 SSA(2)	175	1.8x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.243038049
S9 SAB	207	2.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.315970346
S9 SAB(2)	229	2.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.359835482
S10 NA	101	1.0x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.004321374
S10 NA(2)	112	1.1x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.049218023
S10 MAC	176	1.8x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.245512668
S10 MAC(2)	174	1.7x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.240549248
S10 SSA	125	1.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.096910013
S10 SSA(2)	134	1.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.127104798
S10 SAB	229	2.3x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.359835482
S10 SAB(2)	218	2.2x10 ⁹ CFU/ML	9.338456494

